

TERRA VISION

Integrated Earth Observation Based Platform, for Novel Services
to Enhance the Mining Life Cycle of Critical Raw Materials

D9.3

Development and demonstration of EO-based monitoring of
stockpile volumes and extraction rates (alpha version)

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
ARD	Analysis-Ready Data
AVE	Absolute Volume Estimation
CCM	Copernicus Contributing Missions
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CRM	Critical Raw Material
CRS	Coordinate Reference System
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
InSAR	Interferometric SAR
DL	Deep Learning
DSM	Digital Surface Model
DTM	Digital Terrain Model
EO	Earth Observation
EROM	Extraction Rate Open Cast Mining
EPSG	European Petroleum Survey Group
ERS	Extraction Rate Service
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
ICP	Iterative Closest Point
InSAR	Interferometric SAR
IW	Interferometric Wide
PCD	Point Cloud
RANSAC	Random Sample Consensus
ROI	Region of Interest
RTK	Real Time Kinematic

RVE	Relative Volume Estimation
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
SNAP	Sentinel Application Platform
SLC	Single Look Complex
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle

H1 – EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable reports on the activities within the scope of task T9.3 which will develop one of the Earth Observation (EO) services for the mining industry, namely the extraction rate service for monitoring stockpile volumes. As there were no datasets from Copernicus Contributing Missions (CCM) available for the Greek demo site, this initial version focuses on the review of the capability of the European Space Agency Sentinel-1 Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) to provide a reliable estimation of stockpile volume changes. To this end, a first automated prototype for the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) extraction from Sentinel-1 data was developed along with additional tools for processing point clouds from close-range aerial surveys, which will be used as ground truth and potentially enhance the results from the available satellite platforms.

H2 – GOAL/OBJECTIVES

The main objective of this service (Objective O3) is to ‘provide near real-time monitoring of the volume, extraction rate of critical raw materials and changes in stockpile volumes by employing Copernicus satellite services enhanced with drone aerial imagery’ which is divided in two tasks, sharing a common scope and objective, between the two project phases. The primary goal was to assess the capability of the Sentinel-1 platform to generate the DEM of a stockpile at the Greek demo site, at two different points in time, for which a ground-truth elevation model from close-aerial survey was available.

H3 – METHODOLOGY

The DEM extraction from Sentinel-1 data was based on the workflow proposed by ESA using the Sentinel Application Platform (SNAP). The results from experimentation and testing along with related literature pertaining DEM extraction from satellite platforms and point cloud manipulation will inform the next steps of the project implementation.

H4 – OUTCOMES/CONCLUSIONS

The result of volume change estimation from two DEMs generated using Sentinel-1 data was unreliable, which was expected to a certain extent due to the sensor’s spatial resolution which is very low for the task at hand. Nevertheless, a systematic study will be done using the developed service and Sentinel-1 data in order to describe a use case that is useful in the mining industry and potentially allow the automated long-term monitoring of large sites. In addition, higher resolution data will be acquired via the Copernicus Contribution Missions (CCM), both radar and optical, in order to identify a combination of earth observation data sources that could provide a daily estimation of mining extraction rate and report on the quality of the estimation.

Key outcomes/conclusions in bullet points

1. Close-range aerial platforms carrying RGB cameras or LiDAR sensors are the most reliable and flexible means of monitoring open pit mining activity. This is a standard commercially available service nowadays that can achieve volume estimation with a relative error of 3-5%; nevertheless, achieving daily mobilisation of such resources can become overwhelming.
2. Sentinel-1 cannot provide results of comparable quality, neither on the spatial nor on the temporal resolution that is required but a systematic study on what it can offer to the industry, in terms of the quality of DEM generation, is needed.
3. Data from alternative satellite platforms, both radar and optical (i.e. WorldView3-4, Pleiades Neo, TerraSAR-X), acquired via the Copernicus Contributing Missions will be pursued and utilised in the next phase.
4. Several components for the service, for SAR and point cloud processing, have been implemented. The complete set will be finalised upon integration and testing in the next phase of the project.

1. Introduction

1.1 Deliverable Description

This document describes the development of EO-based monitoring of stockpile volumes and extraction rates. This initial version is focused on reviewing results from studies that have extracted DEM from SAR and how the results compare to the close-range (aerial or terrestrial) methods that were used as ground truth in those studies. A case study using datasets for the TERNAMAG mining site is also provided to showcase the current technological capabilities and justify the next steps.

1.2 Purpose of the Deliverable

The objectives related to this deliverable have been achieved in full and as scheduled, nevertheless, the further effort is required in order to achieve the aim of the corresponding task which is to develop an earth-observation-based extraction-rate monitoring service for mines, document its capabilities and integrate it to the project's platform.

1.3 Intended Audience

The main audience of this deliverable at this stage of the project, in addition to the project's continuous reporting purposes, is the consortium partners that are indirectly involved in the support and integration of the WP9 services to the platform.

1.4 Deliverable Structure and Relation with Other Work Packages and Deliverables

Section 2 provides a review of SAR-based DEM generation studies and the accuracy of the reported results. Section 3 presents a case study for DEM generation of the TERNAMAG site using Sentinel-1 data. Section 4 provides an overview of the extraction rate service and sections 5 and 6 present the development of point cloud processing tools for volume estimation. This work will continue in task T10.3 for the next reporting period. The work in task T5.2 is relevant to this service in terms of providing survey data for the service validation. Work packages WP4 and WP7 are relevant in defining the user interface for the service and the requirements in terms Analysis-Ready Data (ARD).

2. Review of Sentinel-1 Synthetic Aperture Radar for DEM Generation

During the past few years close-range aerial surveys using UAVs have become the standard practice for generating DEMs of open pit mines and stockpiles. The flexibility, and the relatively approachable equipment cost of these platforms, which can carry high resolution cameras and LiDAR sensors as payload, allows them to cover the entire area of interest at resolutions producing point clouds and DEMs of sub-decimeter accuracy resulting to volume estimation between successive surveys at the relative error range of 3-5% (Alsayed & Nabawy, 2023). However, daily monitoring of large mine sites and stockpile areas can introduce difficulties regarding the management and processing of large data-sets or the follow-on costs if these tasks are outsourced. To overcome these challenges, the potential of earth observation platforms is being explored as more sensors are set in orbit. As an indication of the performance of a very high resolution stereo pair, Worldview-3 images with 0.31 m resolution can generate a DEM with a standard deviation compared to LiDAR check points of 0.62 m (Hu et al., 2016). Nevertheless, daily acquisitions of such datasets are challenging and costly. Therefore, the potential of the openly accessible Sentinel-1 data is investigated in order to assess the information that can be extracted to monitor a mining site to infer extraction rate.

2.1 Sentinel-1 for DEM Generation

As one of the most well-known methods for observing changes on Earth's surface, satellite remote sensing using radar provides continuous imaging capabilities for both day and night and all-weather conditions which makes it a valuable tool for detecting ground movements following earthquakes and subsidence and landslides and other such phenomena. The most effective method among these approaches is Synthetic Aperture Radar Interferometry (InSAR). InSAR uses the phase difference between SAR acquisitions to generate DEMs for detecting minute topographic changes. These are naturally sensitive to even minor elevation variations (referring to relative displacements over time), and that sort of sensitivity renders InSAR much more suitable for monitoring any large-scale ground deformation, such as land subsidence or landslide. Conceptually, by producing DEMs at two different time points, it becomes theoretically feasible to obtain changes in volume, hence appropriate for applications where surface topography needs to be monitored repeatedly (Bamler & Hartl, 1998; Franceschetti et al., 2018; Massonnet & Feigl, 1998).

The launch of Sentinel-1 marked a major milestone by providing openly accessible SAR data with routine global coverage. While designed primarily for differential interferometry (DInSAR) focused on surface deformation, Sentinel-1's capability to retrieve DEMs has been the focus of increasing research. In a 2018 study a more than 5-meter errors in Turkish hilly areas was reported as an example of significant difficulties that exist in landscapes with varying elevation patterns (Atalay & Sefercik, 2018). In a 2019 study Sentinel-1 data was used

to generate DEMs of Iran's Kavir desert which revealed elevation accuracy variations between 1.26 meters in plains and 10.32 meters in mountainous regions (Ghannadi et al., 2019).

Braun's 2021 investigation (Braun, 2021) confirmed that DEM extraction depends heavily on short temporal baselines (≤ 12 days) and perpendicular baselines between 150 and 300 meters. Furthermore, stable surface conditions are necessary to maintain coherence. Coherence will diminish rapidly with the introduction of vegetation, water, weather, or dynamic landform characteristics and can limit the fidelity of phase measurements. For example, when using Sentinel-1 to monitor landslides in Iceland, Dabiri et al. (2020) found root-mean-square vertical errors of near 46 meters (as compared to ArcticDEM) due primarily to temporal decorrelation over an unstable slope and insufficient baseline geometry.

Likewise, (Kakavas et al., 2018) investigated karstic terrain of Ksiromero, Greece using Sentinel-1 found root-mean-square errors of nearly 39 meters while only properly identifying 68.8% of karst features. The sources of this error were determined to Sentinel-1's low vertical sensitivity and there was insufficient resolution to adequately represent strongly irregular geomorphology. Together, these studies reveal that such errors frequently occur in regions with intense topographic variation, such as steep slopes, valleys, and mountainous landscapes, where distortions like foreshortening, layover, shadowing, and the cat-eye effect are more likely.

Despite the large variation on the reported quality of the results and the indication that they are mostly not fit for the purpose of accurately monitoring a stockpile's volume change to infer the extraction rate of an open pit mine there may still be value on the data acquired by the Sentinel-1 platform which is worth being investigated. Specifically, the following shortcoming of existing attempts to generate DEM from Sentinel-1 and the way the results were reported (Braun, 2021) are limiting the usefulness of existing studies to come to definitive conclusions :

1. Report the SAR product IDs that were used for DEM generation
2. Report on image dates and perpendicular baselines
3. Report the parameters used in the processing pipeline
4. Include the interferogram and coherence layer
5. Specify which DEM was used as reference and assess its quality
6. Visualize the end product on a map instead of only proving summarized quality metrics at a set of control points
7. Clarity on the results fitness for a specific purpose

3. Estimation of Stockpile Volume Using DEM Generated from Sentinel-1 InSAR Data

The case aimed at the practical feasibility of estimating stockpile volume at the TERNAMAG mining site (Figure 1) with Sentinel-1 InSAR data. The adopted methodological framework was thus largely based on the standard interferometric SAR processing chain, implemented with the ESA SNAP Sentinel Application Platform (European Space Agency, 2025b), with guidance from the "S1TBX DEM generation with Sentinel-1 IW Tutorial" (European Space Agency, 2021). It should be noted that the ground truth stockpile volumes from the drone imagery were available for 6th June 2023, and 16th January 2024. Direct temporal overlap with Sentinel-1 acquisitions was not possible, but in an effort to perform a qualitative comparison, image pairs were deliberately selected with acquisition dates as temporally close as possible with respect to the dates of drone surveys. The ground truth data were provide by TERNAMAG as a result of an aerial photogrammetric survey at a constant above-ground level using on-board GPS-RTK to estimate the initial exterior orientation parameters and for absolute georeferencing of the result. This point cloud has sub-decimeter accuracy and for the scope of this study is considered as absolute ground truth against which the SAR DEM will be compared.

Figure 1. The case study area described herein is the Moraitis stockpile between the TERNAMAG Kakavos material sorting plant (middle) and the Mpompakas/Archangelos open pit mine (top left) in Euboea, Greece. The stockpile approximately covers an 350×350 m area with an elevation range between 100-150m.

The entire processing workflow for generating two different DEMs from Sentinel-1 Interferometric Wide (IW) mode data followed a sequential phase division:

STEP I: DATA SELECTION CHECKING AND PRELIMINARY ASSESSMENT

Figure 2 The complete workflow for processing two DEMs from Sentinel-1 Interferometric Wide (IW) mode data followed a defined sequence. The basic step included the careful selection of two Sentinel-1 Single Look Complex (SLC) image pairs. Selection of interferometric data pairs was guided by their perpendicular (Bperp) and temporal (Btemp) baselines, which are summarized in Table 1 below. Figure 2 provides visual overviews of the selected interferometric pairs.

Table 1. Description of the data sets that were used for DEM generation and validation

Data Type	Acquisition System	Acquisition Date	Temporal Baseline	Perpendicular Baseline (m)	Purpose
SAR (SLC) Image	Sentinel-1A IW Mode	27/06/2023	12 days	-209.79	DEM Generation (Pair 1 – Ref)
SAR (SLC) Image	Sentinel-1A IW Mode	09/07/2023			DEM Generation (Pair 1 – Sec)
SAR (SLC) Image	Sentinel-1A IW Mode	24/12/2023	36 days	-245.30	DEM Generation (Pair 2 – Ref)
SAR (SLC) Image	Sentinel-1A IW Mode	29/01/2024			DEM Generation (Pair 2 – Sec)
DEM	Copernicus DEM (30m)	N/A (static product)	-	-	Reference for elevation calibration
3D Point-Cloud	UAV-based	06/06/2023	-	-	Ground Truth Reference for pair 1
3D Point-Cloud	UAV-based	16/01/2024	-	-	Ground Truth Reference for pair 2

Figure 2. Interferometric pair 1 (left): Sentinel-1A SLC images acquired on June 27, 2023 (reference) and July 9, 2023 (secondary), with a perpendicular baseline (B_{perp}) of -209.79 meters and a temporal baseline (B_{temp}) of 12 days. Interferometric pair 2 (right): Sentinel-1A SLC images acquired on December 24, 2023 (reference) and January 29, 2024 (secondary), with a perpendicular baseline (B_{perp}) of -245.30 meters and a temporal baseline (B_{temp}) of 36 days.

The first pair, obtained on 27 June and 9 July 2023, had a temporal baseline of 12 days and a B_{perp} of -209.79 meters. The second pair, acquired on 24 December 2023 and 29 January 2024, had a longer baseline of 36 days and a B_{perp} of -245.30 meters. While both interferometric pairs satisfied the recommended B_{perp} range (150–300 m) for DEM generation, the 36-day temporal baseline of the second pair significantly exceeded the optimal threshold (≤ 12 days) necessary to preserve coherence. This deviation is particularly ineffective in the context of highly dynamic surfaces, such as those seen in active stockpiles.

STEP 2: COREGISTRATION OF SENTINEL-1 TOPSAR DATA

The coregistration was carefully executed to ensure the sub-pixel accuracy of the selected image pairs, consisting of the following sub-steps:

1. TOPS Split: The S-1 TOPS Split operator was applied to select Sub-Swath IW2 (Fig. 4) and VV polarization, concentrating on burst 5 (Figure 3, right) for each of the products. This step isolated the area of interest.
2. Application of Orbit Information (Apply Orbit File): Precise orbit auxiliary data, crucial for correct satellite positioning, were indeed automatically downloaded and applied to both products.
3. Back Geocoding: The major operation of co-registration of the split products was done using the S-1 Back Geocoding operator. This operation considered the updated orbit information and used the Copernicus 30m Global DEM (Auto Download) as the reference for geocoding. Bilinear interpolation was selected for DEM resampling, and elevation data not available in any area was masked out.

Figure 3. (left) Map highlighting the Area of Interest (AOI) within Sub-Swath IW2 (marked in red). (right) View of the Sentinel-1 IW2 Sub-Swath, with burst 5 (highlighted in red) selected for processing. This burst contains the Area of Interest (AOI) and was used for coregistration in the SAR workflow.

STEP 3: INTERFEROGRAM FORMATION AND COHERENCE ESTIMATION

After successful coregistration, two independent interferograms were formed (Figure 4), each referencing one of the two Sentinel-1 image pairs determined in Phase 1. This was achieved through complex multiplication between the reference image and the complex conjugate of the secondary one, and the resulting phase being in effect the interferometric phase difference. Simultaneously, coherence, which measures the degree of similarity of pixels between two images, was computed as a standalone raster band. These are some key parameters that had been set in this phase: flat-earth phase subtraction, coherence estimation, and importantly, the option for topographic phase subtraction was explicitly not chosen in order to retain elevation information that is essential for DEM generation.

Figure 4. Unfiltered interferogram (June–July pair) showing the wrapped phase difference (in radians) after coregistration and complex multiplication.

STEP 4-INTERFEROGRAM PHASE FILTERING

The Goldstein Phase Filtering operator (Goldstein & Werner, 1998) was applied to increase the signal-to-noise ratio of the generated interferograms (Figure 5) -a prerequisite need for precision in phase unwrapping. This filter uses a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) to suppress noise from temporal and geometric decorrelation, volume scattering, and other types of processing noise from the interferograms, while not affecting the coherence band.

Figure 5. Filtered interferogram after applying the Goldstein Phase Filtering operator to enhance signal-to-noise ratio for phase unwrapping.

STEP 5-PHASE UNWRAPPING

The wrapped phase was then unwrapped, turning the cyclical phase into a continuous absolute phase measurement (Figure 6), in turn, referenceable to topographic height. This process was done using the SNAPHU library (Chen & Zebker, 2000, 2024) using the following parameters: 'TOPO' statistical-cost mode and 200 pixels row/column overlap.

Figure 6. Comparison of wrapped and unwrapped phase after Goldstein filtering and Snaphu unwrapping. Phase before (top) and after (bottom) unwrapping.

STEP 6: PHASE TO ELEVATION CONVERSION

The last step of the DEM generation workflow is to translate the unwrapped phase (measured in radians) to absolute height values in meters (Figure 7). For this, the Phase to Elevation operator was applied over the imported unwrapped phase product. The conversion of the unwrapped phase to elevation used the Copernicus 30m Global DEM¹ as an input DEM, so the absolute elevation level of the derived height values could be set correctly. Each pixel of the output product contained metric elevation values summarizing each pixel's height above sea level. The output DEMs derived from both interferometric pairs were thus georeferenced using the same 30m Copernicus DEM baseline, ensuring consistency between them.

Figure 7. Moraitis stockpile at the TERNAMAG Site and the regional DEM derived from the summer pair (27.06.2023 – 09.07.2024).

2.2 Results and Discussion

The differences in volume between the two InSAR-derived DEMs were minimal, indicating that they failed to accurately reflect actual changes in the stockpile volume. As shown in the following images the two DEM are almost identical with elevation range between 149-236m resulting in elevation differences of approximately 1m. The estimated change was less than 1000 cubic meters whereas the actual volume change for the same period was over 200000 cubic meters.

¹ <https://dataspace.copernicus.eu/explore-data/data-collections/copernicus-contributing-missions/collections-description/COP-DEM>

- Winter DEM, derived from the Dec 24, 2023 – Jan 29, 2024 image pair

Figure 8. Sentinel-1 DEM of the TERAMAG Moraitis stockpile using SAR pair from the 24/12/2023 and 29/01/2024

- Summer DEM, derived from the June 27 – July 9, 2023 image pair

Figure 9. Sentinel-1 DEM of the TERAMAG Moraitis stockpile using SAR pair from the 27/06/2024 and 09/07/2024.

- Volume Estimation, calculated as Winter minus Summer: 809 m³

Figure 10. Difference of Sentinel-1 DEM for the TERAMAG Moraitis stockpile between 12/2023 and 07/2024.

The applications of the Sentinel-1 InSAR processing chain for estimating stockpile volume at the TERNAMAG mining site remained inconclusive and of negligible practical value. The limitations arise from several factors but the main one in this case was the fact that a ten year old base-DEM Copernicus GLO-30 (European Space Agency, 2025a) was used in the processing

which was more than 50 m off in elevation at the specific stockpile area causing the phase unwrapping to fail.

In general, the fact that Sentinel-1's orbital configuration is specifically optimized for deformation monitoring DInSAR, rather than for absolute elevation measurements, is apparent based on the combination of the following key influences:

- **Perpendicular Baseline Constraints:** Sentinel-1's orbital configuration is primarily optimized for DInSAR, which typically results in relatively short perpendicular baselines (often below 50 meters). The pairs selected for this study resulted in B_{perp} of -209.79 m and -245.30 m. These are generally considered acceptable for DEM extraction, however, they resulted from larger than recommended temporal baselines.
- **Temporal Decorrelation:** The temporal baselines were 12.00 days and 36.00 days. The first baselines are acceptable, while the second is still longer than a suitable temporal baseline of 6-12 days for Sentinel-1 InSAR application, especially when monitoring dynamic surfaces such as stockpiles. Material is continuously being added to, moved and unloaded from the stockpiles. In addition, there are always changing environmental conditions (e.g., rainfall, dust storms, wind) and ongoing mining operations. This results in a constantly changing surface when monitoring a stockpile. The changing surface conditions will induce significant temporal decorrelation that will cause noisy interferograms making the phase measurements unreliable to derive a DEM. The 36-day interferogram presented significant temporal decorrelation, evidenced by a mean coherence of 0.33 and a median coherence of 0.31. More than 50% of the imaged pixels fell below the 0.3 reliability threshold, where any material movement was active. Only 10% of the imaged pixels, which fell within this analysis time frame, had coherence greater than 0.54, ultimately limiting usable data to stable ground surfaces. The 12-day pair (June–July 2023) showed marginally better coherence (mean=0.37) than the 36-day pair (mean=0.33), but 50% of pixels remained below 0.37. Only 25% exceeded 0.51 (P75), with just 10% reaching 0.68 (P90). This confirms that even short temporal baselines struggle with stockpile dynamics, as active areas consistently degraded coherence to unreliable levels (<0.3).
- **Spatial Resolution:** Sentinel-1's Interferometric Wide (IW) mode has a native resolution of approximately 5 m×20 m (range × azimuth) in SLC format. The generated DEM products, without applying multilooking, had a pixel size of approximately 13.93 m. This inherent coarse resolution is not sufficient to capture the subtle, steep slopes and complex surface geometry of typical stockpiles, smoothing them too much and resulting in the loss of important fine-scale features important for accurate volume calculation.
- **Ground truth misalignment:** The drone-derived true volume values were acquired on June 6, 2023 and January 16, 2024 and despite the selection of Sentinel-1 acquisitions temporally close to the drone survey dates, the fundamental temporal misalignment means any change to the stockpile that occurred due to operations during the time period of the SAR acquisitions until the drone survey dates could not have been

estimated accurately. This common misalignment will invariably reduce the confidence of use for direct pairwise comparisons for accurate volume estimates.

- Atmospheric and Geometric Distortions: Atmospheric delays which impact radar signals can occur due to changes in humidity, pressure, and temperature. These alterations can mimic or obscure elevation differences in the data. Geometric distortions that are specific to radar (i.e. layover and foreshortening) have a greater impact over features with high relief (i.e. stockpiles) and make the process of generating an accurate DEM over such features even more complicated.

Overall, the combined effects of all of these different limitations made the Sentinel-1 InSAR approach impractical for reliable estimation of stockpile volumes in this operational context on a daily basis. However, as specified in (Braun, 2021) there is a lack of systematic assessment and proper scientific reporting of generated DEM for earthworks monitoring and their quality.

4. Overview of the Extraction Rate Service

The aim of task T9.3, which will be continued and completed in the scope of T10.3, is to develop and deploy an Extraction Rate Service (ERS) for the computation of DEM and relative volume change through the use of optical and SAR images acquired from airborne and spaceborne sensors. Data from aerial platforms will come from the ordinary survey activities of TERNAMAG, which include monthly aerial photogrammetric surveys of the open pit mine and ad-hoc monitoring of the stockpiles, as well as the survey campaigns in the scope of tasks T5.2 and T6.2, as described in deliverable D5.2, in the form of point clouds or DEMs. These datasets will be fed directly to the service to calculate the volume changes and also as ground truth to assess and improve the DEM generation from satellite platforms. In terms of satellite data sources, the main goal is to fully utilize the openly available Sentinel-1 data and provide a systematic assessment of their potential for extraction rate monitoring at mining sites; even if their resolution is not adequate for reliable extraction rate estimation on a daily basis, the question still remains under what circumstances and for which use case or timeframe they are useful. Also, via the exploitation of the project's access to the Copernicus Contributing Missions, very high-resolution optical sensors from platforms such as Worldview and Pleiades-Neo will be utilized for stereoscopic DEM generation and assessment in order to assess their utilization for extraction rate monitoring on a regular basis.

There are two types of users for this service: i) user with view rights (Viewer) who is interested in viewing a timeline of the estimated volumes and ii) a user who can manually upload data (Provider). The Viewer can initiate an instance of the service by selecting an area of interest and also the start date and end date under consideration. The Provider uploads point cloud data, typically from close-range surveying activities, which is converted to DEM and updates the composite DEM of the entire site which will be used as the base DEM for InSAR-based DEM generation. The composite DEM is also the ground truth against which the satellite-generated DEMs are compared to provide an assessment of their reliability.

Figure 11. An overview of the Extraction Rate Service flow.

At this point of the development, the SAR DEM generation pipeline that is described in section 3 is implemented with SNAP utilizing its Command Line Interface (CLI) and Python. Moving forward alternative open sources libraries for SAR data processing will be assessed for the SAR

sub-service to be integrated to the Terravision platform along with complementary sub-services based on optical stereo-pairs. The aspect of the volume calculation as a computational operation was also investigated and a custom-made volume calculation tool has been developed. Its main goal is the acceleration of the volume estimation calculations as the 3D datasets tend to be large. To this end, NVIDIA's CUDA platform is used with the CuPy² Python library to offset the most demanding calculations to a compatible Graphics Processing Unit (GPU). Several tools for aerial point cloud (coming from either photogrammetric or LiDAR surveys) manipulation were implemented to support operations on the platform as required: rasterization of point clouds to DEMs, point cloud and DEM subdivision based on region of interest (ROI) selection, volume calculation between two DEMs, calculation of the volume under a stockpile's surface under the assumption that it lays on a planar surface. These are described in the next section.

² <https://cupy.dev/>

5. Photogrammetric EROM: System Design

5.1 Motivation

The photogrammetric component of the Extraction Rate in Opencast Mining (EROM) service, based on UAV surveys, complements, refines and validates its broader SAR-based counterpart by acquiring centimeter-scale surface detail, far surpassing the resolution of common free satellite products like Sentinel-1. These high-resolution photogrammetric surface models enable accurate stockpile volume assessments and Critical Raw Material (CRM) extraction rate calculations, and act as a surrogate ground truth to calibrate SAR volumetric models, mitigate biases, and strengthen long-term monitoring even when drone coverage is partial. The key operational hurdle is synchronizing drone flights precisely with satellite overpasses. Because photogrammetric point clouds fall outside the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem (CDSE), the EROM service will instead be deployed on the TERRAFUSION platform (see D4.4, Figure 24).

5.2 System Requirements and Architecture Design

The UAV-based component of the EROM service outlined in D4.2 was converted into detailed functional requirements through close collaboration and one-on-one sessions with TERNAMAG, the service's lead demonstrator. Following thorough discussions, it was agreed that the aforementioned component is expected to support two core operations:

1. Processing point-cloud pairs by photogrammetric surveys of the dump site to calculate relative volume changes over fixed time intervals (≤ 12 days).
2. Optional handling of user-specified regions of interest (e.g., resembling stockpiles) to compute their absolute volumes on demand.

Finally, the design and development of the EROM service were carried out in compliance with requirement R3 (sustainability and resilience of mining operations) as described in Table 2 of D4.1.

The architecture component diagram initially introduced in Deliverable D4.4 (Figure 17) has since been revised. Two distinct but complementary architectures have been developed: one dedicated to relative volume estimation (Figure 12 left) and the other focused on absolute volume estimation (Figure 12 right). Both serve similar objectives but are tailored to different types of volumetric analysis.

The Relative Volume Estimation (RVE) pipeline starts with offline training of a 2D vehicle-and-vegetation detector on drone-derived orthophotos, with transfer-learning updates applied as new data become available. For each pair of georeferenced point-clouds, typically captured two weeks apart over TERNAMAG's Moraitis dumping site, the 3D data are first converted into a validated orthophoto (with optional tiling at 640×640 resolution for detection). The detector then flags vegetation and vehicles, and the Surface-to-Terrain converter realigns their elevations to the surrounding ground, so they do not skew the volume estimation. Next, the XY plane is divided into a regular grid, the average point height difference in each cell is multiplied by its area to compute per-cell volume change, and these voxel volumes are summed to produce the net volume difference. Finally, dividing that net change by the time

interval yields the relative volume estimation rate. As anticipated, shorter intervals between photogrammetric surveys yield higher temporal resolution in the resulting extraction rate.

Figure 12. Relative (left) and Absolute (right) Volume Estimation Architectures.

The Absolute Volume Estimation (AVE) pipeline starts with a single georeferenced point-cloud and an offline-trained 2D stockpile detector (with on-demand transfer-learning updates as new data arrive). After generating the corresponding orthophoto, the user delineates one or more regions of interest, via simple drag-and-drop, to capture each stockpile and its surrounding ground. The surrounding ground is essential for the advanced plane-stockpile separation developed based on the RANSAC algorithm. Those ROI-filtered points are then passed through a surface reconstruction algorithm (e.g., Alpha Shapes, Poisson reconstruction, Ball-Pivoting Algorithm or Delaunay triangulation) to build a mesh. By subdividing that mesh into triangular prisms and summing their individual volumes, the pipeline computes the absolute volume of each selected stockpile.

5.3 Sequence Diagrams

The sequence diagram depicted in Figure 13 illustrates the RVE pipeline. First, the mining operator, e.g., TERNAMAG, exports raw drone images and photogrammetric point-clouds (PCDs); the images feed into an Image Annotation step whose output, annotated images, is used to continuously fine-tune the Vehicle/Vegetation Detector via transfer learning. As the number of photogrammetric surveys increases and more annotated images become available, the detector's accuracy in identifying vehicles and vegetation steadily improves (an essential capability for robust surface-to-terrain conversion to strip out unwanted vegetation or moving-vehicle noise from volume estimates). Raw point-clouds go directly into the 3D processing stage where operations such as downsampling take place. Those processed point-clouds, along with the detector's orthomosaics and marked regions of interest (ROIs), then feed into the 2D orthophoto processing workflow. Here, images are filtered by ROI and object masks, and an Ortho-to-PCD converter applies the same filters in 3D to produce refined point-clouds with segmented objects of interest. Next, these filtered point-clouds undergo Surface-to-Terrain conversion before entering the Relative Volume Estimator, which computes both

the change in volume (in m³) and the extraction rate, returning these metrics to the operator. Flying the drone more frequently simply improves the temporal resolution of the extraction-rate.

Figure 13. Relative Volume Estimation.

The sequence diagram in Figure 14 outlines the AVE estimation pipeline: the mining operator, e.g., TERNAMAG, first dispatches raw point-clouds (PCDs), orthomosaics, and user-defined stockpile polygons to the processing pipeline. Similarly, to the RVE, the 3D PCD Processing module ingests the PCDs, cleaning, filtering, and geo-referencing them, and then forwards the processed PCDs, along with the orthomosaic imagery and the polygon footprint, to the 2D Orthophoto Generation/Processing stage. Here, the stockpile polygon is used to mask the orthophoto, yielding a polygon-filtered image that the Ortho-to-PCD Converter transforms back into a localized “stockpile” point-cloud. That refined point-cloud is sent to Surface Reconstruction, which builds a triangular mesh representation of the stockpile’s surface. Finally, the Absolute Volume Estimator computes the mesh’s enclosed volume (in m³) and reports the result back to the mining operator.

Figure 14. Absolute Volume Estimation.

5.4 Technology and Tools Used

In this initial release, a standalone EROM desktop application has been developed in Python using an OpenCV-based interface, which has not yet been integrated with the TERRAFUSION platform. For 3D point-cloud processing, Open3D is leveraged to handle data acquired via

drone photogrammetry, including its accompanying orthomosaic, or directly from LiDAR scans, which are typically supplied without one. Crucially, orthophotos can still be generated internally for manual or automated ROI selection, incurring only a modest processing-time overhead while enabling a substantial reduction in data transfer; only the point-cloud and a subset of raw images need be uploaded to the TERRAFUSION backend, rather than bulky orthomosaics.

In the future the TERRAFUSION backend could host all historical point-clouds in *pgPointCloud*, the PostgreSQL extension optimized for storing and querying large LiDAR datasets, so operators only need to upload the latest scan; the system can then fetch any previous point-cloud directly from the database to perform on-demand volume-change comparisons.

Table 2 provides a representative sample of the Python packages used in the EROM service, along with brief descriptions of their functionality and their specific roles.

Table 2. Python packages used in the EROM service.

Python package	Primary Function	Role in EROM Desktop-app
PyTorch (torch)	Deep Learning (DL) framework with GPU acceleration	Powers tensor-based volume-change computations and supports training/fine-tuning of custom neural modules.
YOLOv8	State-of-the-art real-time object detection	Employed for both offline training and live inference of the vehicle & vegetation detector on orthophotos.
Open3D	3D data processing, point-cloud & mesh management	Handles point-cloud I/O, RANSAC-based plane segmentation, outlier removal, Poisson/Delaunay surface reconstruction, etc.
OpenCV	Computer-vision & GUI toolkit	Provides a lightweight ROI-selection interface and manages PNG export of intermediate views (planes, meshes, etc.)
Pillow	Image loading & manipulation	Performs orthophoto padding, tiling, format conversion, and pre-processing before detection or reprojection.
pyproj	Coordinate reference transformations	Converts between projected CRS (e.g., EPSG:2100) and WGS84 for accurate geo-referencing and Google Maps checks.
GDAL	Raster/vector geospatial I/O	Reads/writes orthomosaics, computes & caches raster statistics in auxiliary XML files for fast metadata access.
laspy	LAS/LAZ LiDAR file handling	Loads raw .las/.laz files and exports them as open3d.geometry.PointCloud objects for downstream processing.
SciPy	Scientific computing & algorithms	Implements constrained Delaunay triangulation for mesh-based volume estimation.
NumPy	Core numerical operations on n-dimensional arrays	Serves as the backbone for all array/matrix math throughout the pipeline (from point-cloud stats to image ops).

CuPy	NumPy-compatible GPU arrays	Accelerates tensor-based volume computations on NVIDIA GPUs via CUDA.
scikit-learn	ML utilities	Applies DBSCAN clustering for stockpile isolation and noise filtering within ROIs.

5.5 Deployment and Runtime Environment

The experiments were conducted on a laptop running Ubuntu 22.04 equipped with an Intel Core i7-12650H processor (10 cores, 16 threads, up to 4.7 GHz). The system was paired with an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 4050 GPU featuring 6 GB of GDDR6 memory.

The EROM application is executed within a Python 3.10 virtual environment, with all libraries (OpenCV, Open3D, PyTorch, etc.) installed via pip and GPU support provided by CUDA 12.8 and the RTX 4050 driver stack. At present, it is distributed as a self-contained desktop package without formal containerization; future work may include a lightweight Docker image (using NVIDIA's runtime) to simplify deployment on the TERRAFUSION platform. Scalability is currently limited to a single machine, relying on Open3D's multi-threading and CUDA concurrency to exploit all 10 CPU cores and the GPU, but could later be extended through container orchestration (e.g., Kubernetes or Docker Compose) for parallel processing of multiple survey tiles or time-series batches.

6. Photogrammetric EROM: Evaluation of Developed Features

6.1 Data Sources and Preparation

Open3D's surface reconstruction routines were employed to process two georeferenced point-clouds of the Moraitis dump site (see Open3D-based visualizations in Figure 15), acquired on different dates, in order to quantify the net positive volume increase due solely to material deposition. To eliminate accumulation artifacts observed at the Mpompakas mining sites (Figure 16) due to transient water, only surveys captured at the Moraitis dump site were selected. The point-cloud density was set at 0.12 m by TERNAMAG topographers, providing sufficient spatial resolution across the $\sim 138128 \text{ m}^2$ dump site without generating unwieldy datasets, and was subsequently validated via KDTree-based average nearest-neighbor analysis in accordance with TERNAMAG specifications.

Figure 15. Moraitis dump site in Euboea, 2023-06-06 (left) and 2024-01-16 (right) visualized with Open3D.

In contrast, Mpompakas mining point-clouds showed water pooling in some surveys but not in others, potentially simulating additional floor excavation and inflating extraction estimates (Figure 15), a pattern reflecting Greece's rainy autumn versus dry summer. Concentrating monitoring on magnesite deposit areas, where such water-related distortions are rare, will produce more reliable measurements of true extraction volumes.

Figure 16. Mpompakas mining site in Euboea. 20-10-2023 (top), 27-06-2024 (bottom).

Figure 17. Bounding box (left) and polygon (right) regions of interest manually selected.

6.2 Manual Region-of-Interest Selection

The generated orthophoto is first scaled to fit the user's display while preserving the original aspect ratio of the point-cloud. When bounding boxes or polygons are drawn on this resized image, their coordinates are transformed back into the orthophoto's native coordinate system (e.g., EPSG:2100 which is the projected coordinate system for Greece and the one the TERNAMAG topographers had been using when generating their photogrammetric point-

clouds), allowing the user to identify and extract the exact 3D points in the point-cloud that fall within each region. If the user does not specify any region of interest, the system defaults to using the entire georeferenced point-cloud, which TERNA has already pre-cropped to a consistent area, for the volume change computation. An example of the two possible manual ROI selection (bounding-box based and polygon based) the developed application offers are illustrated in Figure 17.

6.3 Orthophoto Accuracy Assessment with QGIS

Orthophotos are produced from the point-clouds using Greece’s EPSG-2100 projection, capturing precise terrain snapshots for each photogrammetric survey. Their geometric accuracy is verified by overlaying them on the Google Terrain layer in QGIS³ (see Figure 18). Magnesite extraction occurs at Mpompakas and Archangelos, while Moraitis functions as the dump site, its positive volume changes forming the basis of T9.3 analyses. Generated to abide by topographic standards, these orthophotos facilitate object detection for surface-to-terrain conversion and remain suitable for other mapping applications (e.g., slope stability and erosion monitoring).

Figure 18. Google Terrain layer on QGIS (left), orthophoto layers of Mpompakas mining site and Moraitis dump site on top of Google Terrain layer on QGIS (right).

The accuracy of the orthophoto scale can be further validated by using QGIS’s measure-line tool to compare a dump truck’s known physical dimensions with its pixel representation (see Figure 19), thereby confirming that the generated pixels correspond to the correct real-world measurements.

³ <https://qgis.org/>

Figure 19. Measured trunk length 10.25 m (left), measured trunk width 4.76 m (right) with QGIS measure line.

6.4 Relative Volume Estimation

6.4.1 Introduction

The Relative Volume Estimation (RVE) task involves measuring the volume change between two georeferenced point-clouds of the Moraitis dump site, acquired on 6 June 2023 and 16 January 2024 (see Figure 15). A reference volume change of 258891 m³, obtained via TERNAMAG’s professional surveying tools (e.g., GEOVIA Surpac or PIX4D), is employed for evaluation. Two methodologies have been attacked: (1) mesh-based volume differencing via constrained Delaunay triangulation, and (2) a raster-grid approach operating directly on point-clouds.

6.4.2 Preprocessing: Surface-to-Terrain Conversion

Collaboration with TERNAMAG revealed that vegetation and mobile machinery captured during photogrammetric surveys can introduce substantial noise into volume estimates. Because manually removing these objects from the point-cloud is labor-intensive, a semi-automated surface-to-terrain conversion pipeline is under investigation. Nevertheless, it is not expected to reach the same level of maturity as the core volume-estimation workflows.

For the sake of simplicity and controllability in the proof of concept, the Moraitis point-cloud from 6 June 2023 (Figure 15, left) was first cropped to a smaller area containing only the stockpiles, surrounding bushes, two dump trucks, and an excavator (Figure 20, top left). When the corresponding Digital Elevation Model (DEM) was generated (Figure 20, top right), it was observed that vehicles and vegetation remained, resulting actually in a Digital Surface Model (DSM). Consequently, the “Surface-to-Terrain Conversion” submodule was employed to remove any transient or static objects not belonging to the terrain so that stockpile volume estimation would not be corrupted.

An object detector was applied to the orthophoto (Figure 20, middle left) to locate only two classes, namely ‘vegetation’ and ‘vehicle’, and the corresponding 3D points within each bounding box were extracted by the “Ortho-to-PCD Converter” module (Figure 20, middle right). Each object's footprint was slightly expanded (highlighted in red) to capture adjacent

ground, and a best-fit plane was calculated for each ground patch (as described in Section 3.5.B).

In the final step, Z-coordinates of all non-plane points (i.e., those corresponding to detected vehicles or vegetation) were sampled from a Gaussian distribution defined by the best-fit plane's mean (μ) and standard deviation (σ), rather than being uniformly set. By this probabilistic adjustment, a more natural height profile was produced. As shown in Figure 20 (bottom left), the modified points were made to conform to the underlying terrain morphology while statistical variability was retained, thereby eliminating any spurious volume artifacts. Finally, a proper Digital Terrain Model (DTM) was produced (Figure 20, bottom right), upon which safe stockpile volume estimation can be performed.

Figure 20. Cropped point-cloud (top left), DSM (top right), 2D vehicle and vegetation detection (middle left), 3D vehicle and vegetation segmentation (middle right), surface-to-terrain point-cloud (bottom left), DTM (bottom right).

6.4.3 Preprocessing: Synthetic Data Generation

Notably, in the absence of sufficiently large, annotated datasets, top-down orthophotos of mining sites were synthetically generated using text-to-image diffusion models and in particular the Stable Diffusion XL (SDXL) ensemble (Hugging Face: [stabilityai/stable-diffusion-xl-base-1.0](https://huggingface.com/stabilityai/stable-diffusion-xl-base-1.0) + [stabilityai/stable-diffusion-xl-refiner-1.0](https://huggingface.com/stabilityai/stable-diffusion-xl-refiner-1.0)). Systematic prompt engineering was employed to maximize scene realism (see Figure 21), as minor variations in textual input can substantially affect object morphology and scene composition. However, prompt engineering was only lightly explored here, even though it's a whole discipline that needs more dedicated

effort. To facilitate reproducibility, the positive and negative prompts used to generate the synthetic images in Figure 21 are listed below:

Prompt: *A high-resolution, top-down drone view of a magnesite quarry with accurately scaled dump trucks, excavators, and clearly distinguishable magnesite stockpiles. Sparse pine trees and bushes surround the rocky terrain. Bright daylight, realistic shadows, and proper proportions between vehicles, stockpiles, and the landscape. Nadir view, vertical overhead perspective, UHD*

Neg-prompt: *tilted view, side perspective, oblique angles, blurry, out of focus, low resolution, cartoonish, unrealistic proportions, unnatural or exaggerated lighting, artificial shadows, oversaturated colors, abstract, painting-like, fisheye effect, wide-angle distortion, drawing, cgi, unreal engine, animation, water, horizon, skewed view*

Figure 21. A set of images generated from text-to-image diffusion models.

Unfortunately, the synthetic images frequently violated the negative-prompt constraint against tilted perspectives and failed to approximate the strictly nadir (top-down) view characteristic of true orthophotos.

Synthetic orthophotos were meant for annotation, either manual or automatic, and added to the vehicle/vegetation detector’s training set to boost mean average precision and robustness across diverse vehicles and vegetation. Figure 22 shows this annotation workflow using an online agentic object detection system from landing.ai, in which each class was detected in two sequential passes (the online tool supports only one class per inference). Initial tests showed that model quantization (to fit limited GPU memory) degraded image fidelity, although next-generation diffusion models and stronger hardware should produce higher-quality synthetics. For now, it was judged better to overfit on the small real dataset than to dilute it with unrealistic synthetic images.

Figure 22. Automatic annotation of set of images generated from text-to-image diffusion models.

6.4.4 Mesh-Based RVE

Each point-cloud is downsampled (approximately 66 % reduction at a 0.25 m voxel size) and converted into a mesh using constrained Delaunay triangulation. Volume under each triangular facet is computed relative to the Z=0 plane and summed to yield an absolute volume per epoch; the difference between epochs provides the volume change estimate. Processing times vary from ~150 s (0.1 m voxel) to < 8 s (5-20 m voxels), while volumetric error ranges from 0.3 % up to > 2 %. Non-monotonic error behavior arises from noise reduction and triangulation artifacts: an optimal voxel size balances detail retention against smoothing. As meshes are not watertight (continuous, closed surface with no gaps), only differential volumes are deemed reliable.

6.4.5 Raster-Grid Point-Cloud RVE

Following initial registration with Iterative Closest Point (ICP) and optional voxel-grid downsampling to reduce noise, each point-cloud is orthographically projected onto the horizontal (XY) plane. The planar footprint is then subdivided into a regular grid, with cell size dictated by the user-configurable *ve_grid_step* parameter. Within each cell, the mean elevation is computed for both the earlier and later scans; the difference in mean heights is multiplied by the cell's ground area to yield a per-cell volume change. Summing over all cells produces the total volumetric difference without ever constructing a 3D mesh. Because this raster-grid approach scales linearly with point count and avoids expensive triangulation, it completes in under ten seconds even at fine resolutions. In practice, setting the grid step to 1.5 m or less ensures sub-1% error, provided that the grid size remains at least twice the downsampling voxel size, thereby guaranteeing at least two points per cell for a stable height average, and balances spatial detail against statistical robustness.

6.4.6 Benchmark against CloudCompare

Error rates decline as the grid-step is reduced when benchmarked against TERNAMAG's reference volumes; however, a minimum grid-step is required to ensure at least three to four points per cell in each point-cloud for the estimates to remain valid. The implemented raster-grid approach consistently outperforms the CloudCompare benchmark under these conditions (see Figure 23). Calculation speed was nearly doubled with a 50% downsampling of the point-clouds, without any significant loss in accuracy.

Figure 23. RVE vs Grid-step (left), RVE-error vs Grid-step (right).

6.4.7 Experimental Evaluation – Volume Change Estimation

For routine RVE tasks, the raster-grid point-cloud method is advised due to its speed, simplicity, and sub-1 % accuracy at practical resolutions. The mesh-based approach remains available when absolute volumes are required, although it demands longer runtimes and careful voxel-size selection. Robust results depend on accurate ICP alignment, choosing grid steps larger than the downsampling voxel size, and enforcing a minimum point count per cell. Figure 24 illustrates the results with respect to the volume change between the two point-clouds from Figure 15. Uniform color mapping was applied to the point-clouds to more clearly illustrate height differences. The 16 January 2024 (colored in purple) point-cloud clearly indicates a significant downslope displacement of material toward the cliff face.

Figure 24. RVE aggregated results.

Several of the metrics displayed in Figure 20 were adopted from CloudCompare, an open-source tool employed as the reference for benchmarking.

The *grid-step* determines the resolution of the raster grid used for volume estimation: larger steps yield coarser, and therefore less accurate, results. Ideally, the smallest feasible step should be chosen, but this is constrained by point-cloud density. The average number of neighbors per cell should remain around eight; lower values indicate gaps in the grid that can distort volume estimates. In this study, grid steps of 2 m or less consistently produced reliable volume measurements.

The *matching-cells* metric reflects the degree of spatial overlap between the two point-clouds. Since the TERNAMAG datasets cover the identical region at different times, over 90 % of cells coincide across all tested grid steps.

Higher average points per cell tend to reduce accuracy due to excessive aggregation, whereas a minimum of two to three points per cell is necessary to ensure stable volume estimates.

6.5 Absolute Volume Estimation

6.5.1 Introduction

Although relative volume estimation, wherein two time-separated scans are compared, remains a common practice, absolute volume estimation of a single stockpile has been identified for specific use cases such as inventory audits and regulatory reporting. Interest from TERNAMAG, motivated the investigation of the performance of the absolute estimation pipeline described herein.

From the point-cloud acquired on 06-06-2023 for the Moraitis dump site (Figure 15, left), a subset of points was cropped to include a candidate stockpile and its immediate surrounding, relatively horizontal ground. Unlike the relative volume estimation case, where TERNAMAG supplied a benchmark volume change between the two scans in Figure 15, no absolute volume reference existed for the stockpile depicted in Figure 25. Therefore, the CloudCompare-derived volume of 4573 m³ was adopted as the reference (see Figure 26), and a success threshold was set at an error below 5%.

Figure 25. Cropped region from 06-06-2023 Moraitis point-cloud resembling candidate stockpile with surrounding ground.

Figure 26. CloudCompare reference volume of the candidate stockpile

6.5.2 Methodology

The cropped point-cloud of Figure 11 was first normalized by centering it at the origin and adjusting the minimum elevation to zero, thereby establishing a consistent reference for the subsequent operations.

An advanced plane segmentation routine was then applied using an iterative RANSAC approach: candidate planes were extracted (see Figure 27), and the best plane (see Figure 28) was selected by computing a composite score based on average height, flatness, slope, and point count.

Figure 27. Candidate planes after Iterative RANSAC.

Figure 28. Best plane together with the equation describing it and some statistics.

After having identified the best plane, the remaining points of the point-cloud are classified into three categories:

- **Additional Plane Points:** points whose heights fall within a specified tolerance around the “best plane” height. First, the mean height (μ) and its standard deviation (σ) are computed from the points belonging to the best plane. A tolerance factor, such as one or two standard deviations, is then applied, and every point whose height lies within that range around the mean is included. Roughly 68 % of the inliers are captured when using one standard deviation, and about 95 % when using two. In this way, a more tightly clustered, robust set of points around the dominant plane is produced.
- **Stockpile Points:** points located significantly above the best plane, indicative of stockpile material.
- **Noise points:** points that fall below the height range of the best plane, generally considered irrelevant or erroneous data. These points are entirely ignored in the subsequent volumetric estimation pipeline.

Figure 29 illustrates the plane expansion approach. Under the assumption that the points of the best plane are normally distributed and using the 68–95–99.7 rule of statistics (almost all data points fall within three standard deviations of the average), two crucial thresholds to expand the best plane upwards ($\mu+3\sigma$) and downwards ($\mu-3\sigma$) have been identified. By this approach, a stockpile containing fewer statistical outliers is obtained, with outliers typically being those associated with the plane derived via a single, non-iterative RANSAC method. As a result, the stockpile data is rendered cleaner and more representative of the actual stockpile, and the accuracy of subsequent analyses and volume estimation is thereby significantly enhanced.

Figure 29. Best plane expansion logic.

The enhanced best plane after following the best plane expansion explained above is shown in Figure 30 middle. The points shown in green represent the additional plane points fitting the gaussian bell and constrained from the upper and lower limits identified by the 68-95-99.7 rule of statistics. Through the aforementioned procedures, a robust plane segmentation was achieved (see Figure 30 right), and all points rendered in blue were classified as candidate stockpile points.

Figure 30. Advanced Plane Segmentation. Best plane (left), enhanced plane (middle), plane segmentation (right).

Once the ground plane had been removed, the remaining off-plane points, including the stockpile and various noise artefacts, were subjected to a two-stage clean-up and grouping process.

First, a statistical outlier filter was applied: for each point, the average distance to its k nearest neighbours was computed, and any point whose mean distance exceeded a set threshold (typically the overall mean plus $1 \times$ standard deviation) was discarded. This step effectively suppressed isolated spikes and measurement noise while preserving the true pile geometry.

Next, the denoised cloud was fed into DBSCAN, a density-based clustering algorithm that links together points lying within an ϵ -radius neighborhood and rejects clusters smaller than a

minimum size. Once clustering was complete, the principal cluster containing over 80 % of the remaining points, was officially identified as the stockpile.

Surface reconstruction was performed on the principal cluster (Figure 31 left) to convert the point-cloud into a mesh, with three heuristic algorithms, constrained Delaunay triangulation, Poisson reconstruction, and the Ball-Pivoting algorithm, being implemented. Owing to the ill-posed nature of surface reconstruction, constrained Delaunay triangulation was favored for stockpile data, as its 2.5D approach exploits the fact that no two points share identical x–y coordinates: the cloud is projected onto the XY-plane, triangulated in two dimensions (see Figure 31 middle), and then the resulting triangles are restored to their original 3D heights (see Figure 31 right).

Figure 31. 2D Principal DBSCAN cluster (left), constrained Delaunay triangulation (middle), 3D restored triangles (right).

6.5.3 Experimental Results – Volume Estimation

The 3D reconstructed mesh (Figure 31 right) consists of prisms as the one depicted in Figure 32. For each prism, its three vertices were ordered by elevation and oriented so that its projected base on the horizontal plane had a consistent, positive area sign. The area of this base was determined from the two-dimensional projection of the triangle, and the prism’s volume was obtained by multiplying that area by the average height of its three vertices. By summing the volumes of all individual prisms, the total stockpile volume was efficiently and accurately estimated (see Figure 33) with an approximately 3% error compared to the CloudCompare reference volume.

Figure 32. Triangle on reconstructed stockpile surface with XY projections.

Figure 33. Absolute Volume Estimation results

In conclusion, the volumes and heights estimated by the AVE pipeline were closely aligned with those produced by CloudCompare, reinforcing the reliability of the developed approach. When CloudCompare results were treated as ground truth, the height difference yielded an error of approximately 12%, while the volume discrepancy remained below 3.1%; well within acceptable bounds for practical applications. The slightly reduced height estimates of the proposed AVE pipeline can be attributed to the deliberate expansion of the base plane during outlier removal, a necessary trade-off that prioritizes noise suppression over strict vertical precision. Future work will investigate how varying the extent of this plane expansion affects volumetric accuracy and will extend validation to larger stockpiles with independently measured ground-truth data.

7. Conclusion

Two complementary volumetric-analysis pipelines have been implemented and validated. In the Relative Volume Estimation (RVE) workflow, paired, georeferenced point-clouds are automatically ingested; vegetation and vehicles are identified and support the surface-to-terrain conversion; height differences are calculated on a regular grid; and extraction-rate estimates with under 1 % error at operational resolutions are produced. The absolute volume estimation (AVE) pipeline enables single-scan stockpile quantification by combining user-defined regions of interest with advanced RANSAC-based plane segmentation and 2.5D Delaunay surface reconstruction, yielding total volumes within 3 % of CloudCompare benchmarks. Both architectures are implemented in a standalone Python application that leverages Open3D for 3D processing and OpenCV for orthophoto handling, and which has demonstrated robustness across photogrammetric and LiDAR inputs.

Looking ahead, semi-automated surface-to-terrain conversion is being explored to address noise from vegetation and vehicles, although it is acknowledged that this module will require substantial expert oversight and is not expected to mature as rapidly as the core volume-estimation workflows. More point-cloud pairs are anticipated from TERNAMAG, so far only one pair has been used, and these additional datasets will enable further validation of temporal resolution and extraction-rate accuracy. Deployment currently relies on a self-contained desktop package running under Ubuntu 22.04, with future plans to introduce lightweight containerization for simplified integration into the TERRAFUSION platform. Additional work will focus on expanding annotated datasets, refining prompt-engineering practices for synthetic orthophotos, and conducting larger-scale validations against ground-truth data to enhance both accuracy and scalability.

While it is possible to generate DEMs from Sentinel-1, there are inherent limitations of this method for applications that require the ability to estimate fine-scale elevation change for volume estimation mainly due to its spatial resolution. Nevertheless, there may still be value in the data acquired by the Sentinel-1 platform which is worth being investigated; especially now that a second satellite, the Sentinel-1C is in orbit together with Sentinel-1A, replacing the Sentinel-1B which failed in 2021. The challenge is to identify and formulate a use case that is fit for purpose through the systematic long-term assessment of the acquired data against more accurate measurements which are available for the TERNAMAG site in Euboea. In parallel, alternate data sources will be pursued, such as commercial satellite optical stereo imagery (e.g. Worldview or Pleiades).

Close range measurements, including aerial photogrammetric surveys, and potentially terrestrial laser scanning, will be scheduled, in collaboration with TERNAMAG, to coincide with satellite data collection. These will be used as ground truth data for verification and as auxiliary data to improve the results. The surveyed areas will cover a larger part of the demo site, including: i) Mpompakas and Archangelos open pit mines; ii) a flat area adjacent to Archangelos used as a waste dump; iii) the Moraitis stockpile slope which is also a waste dump receiving material. In addition, among the most promising techniques for the resolution of some of the SAR-specific drawbacks would be the application of TerraSAR-X data. TerraSAR-X, especially in its bistatic configuration with TanDEM-X, achieves much higher spatial

resolution (e.g., 1-meter DEMs) and the ability to record single-pass interferometric pairs which greatly minimize temporal decorrelation and atmospheric interference, thereby allowing more stable and accurate elevation measurements for changing areas such as stockpiles.

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